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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF 'STUDY CONTEXT INSECURITY' IN UPPER AND LOWER CLASS YOUTH

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Keywords: Insecurity; Study context Insecurity;
F-Anova test

Abstract:

Present study represents a comparative account of 'Insecurity' in upper and lower class youth. Here we have chosen 18 to 35 years old fellows in both upper and lower class category. Insecurity measurement was carried out by using 'Scale of Insecurity' created by Dr. Beena Shah. After statistical analysis of all data, we found vast different in degree of Insecurity between Upper and lower class youth. We have studied study context Insecurity by taking three independent variables using F-Anova test with 2x2x2 factorial design

Introduction:

The word 'SCHOOL' is derived from Greek word 'SCHOLA'. 'SCHOLA' means sort of meeting where people get together and discuss on some pre-decided topics. The interaction of thoughts of different types of mind was occurred. Such types of interaction were cause deposition of either inferiority or superiority complexes in people's mind. It is categorized as man verses man interaction. It is inferiority complex created by biotic factor. When man does not satisfy his basic requirements during study, he gradually develops Inferiority complex in his mind. And

this Inferiority complex gradually develops in to 'Insecurity'. Insecurity means "The Inferiority complex created due to the external factors/ catalysis of surrounding environment". There are main three types of Insecurity: Social Insecurity, Psychological Insecurity and Ecological Insecurity. Here we try to measure the degree of Insecurity in higher and lower class youth. We mainly focused our study on 'Study context Insecurity' (Raja, 1982).

Objectives:

1. To measure degree of Study context Insecurity in upper and lower class youth
2. To compare degree of Study context Insecurity between upper and lower class youth

Research Methodology:

(Dhila, 2004; Shah, 1989)

1. Independent Variables

A = Economical Status	A ₁ = Upper class (Annual income more than 20,000 rupees)
	A ₂ = Lower class (Annual income less than 20,000 rupees)
B = Area\Location	B ₁ = City (Town)
	B ₂ = Rural
C = Sex	C ₁ = Boys
	C ₂ = Girl

2. Dependent Variables

Degree of Study context Insecurity

Hypothesis:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between Means(M) of the degree of Study context Insecurity between Upper and lower class youth.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between Means(M) of the degree of Study context Insecurity between city and rural area youth.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between Means(M) of the degree of Study context Insecurity between boys and girls.

Tools:

1. Personal information sheet
2. Insecurity measurement scale (Dr. Beena Shah)
3. Statistical analysis of data by F-Anova test using 2x2x2 factorial design

Sample: Total 240 youngsters were selected. Out of 240, 120 were of Upper class and 120 were of lowerclass. Out of these 120, 60 were from city/town area and 60 were from rural area. Sex ratio was maintained 1:1 in these sample of 60. It means out of these 60, 30 were boys and 30 were girls.

Statistical analysis: (Parekh and Dixit, 1995)

Table -1

Summary of the 2x2x2 analysis of variance based on degree of Study context Insecurity with respect to three independent variables

Score of Variable	Sum of Square	DF	Mean of Square	F	Sig.
Status (A)	160.07	1	160.07	13.25	0.01
Aria (B)	3.27	1	3.27	2.70	0.01
Sex (C)	15.00	1	15.00	1.24	N.S.
A x B	1.35	1	1.35	1.12	N.S.
B x C	36.81	1	36.81	3.04	N.S.
A x C	46.40	1	46.40	3.85	N.S.
A x B x C	86.40	1	86.40	7.12	0.01

Table -2

Mean Scores and difference of Mean degree of Study context Insecurity with respect to three independent variables

Independent Variables		N	Mean (M)	Difference Of Mean
Status (A)	Upper	120	70.09	1.63
	Lower	120	5.46	
Aria (B)	City (Town)	120	6.16	0.24
	Rural	120	6.40	
Sex (C)	Boys	120	6.03	0.5
	Girls	120	6.53	

Results and Discussion:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between Means(M) of the degree of Study context Insecurity between Upper and lower class youth.

The 'F-Value' for first set of independent variable was found 13.25 as shown in table-1. This result has 0.01 significance value. So above said hypothesis Ho₁ can not be accepted because result has significant difference. Thus statistical data of table-1 clearly shown that there is significant difference in the degrees of Study context Insecurity between Upper and lower class youth. Mean values for Upper and lower class were 7.09 and 5.46 respectively (Table-2). These mean values concluded that the degree of Study context Insecurity is significantly higher in upper class than that in lower class youth.

Ho₂:

There is no significant difference between Means(M) of the degree of Study context Insecurity between city and rural area youth.

The 'F - Value' for second set of independent variable was found 2.70 as shown in table-1. This result has 0.01 significance value. So above said hypothesis Ho₂ can not be accepted because result has significant difference. Thus statistical data of table-1 clearly shown that there is significant difference in the degrees of Study context Insecurity between city and rural area youth. Mean values for city and rural area were 6.16 and 6.40 respectively (Table-2). These mean values concluded that the degree of Study context Insecurity is significantly higher in rural area than that city area youth.

Ho₃:

There is no significant difference between Means(M) of the degree of Study context Insecurity between boys and girls.

The 'F - Value' for first independent variable was found 1.24 as shown in table-1.

This result has insignificant value. So above said hypothesis H_0 can be accepted because result has significant difference. Thus statistical data of table-1 clearly shown that there is insignificant difference in the degrees of Study context Insecurity between boys and girls. Mean values for Upper and lower class were 6.03 and 6.53 respectively (Table-2). These mean values concluded that the difference in degree of Study context Insecurity is insignificant between girls and boys.

Conclusion:

Finally we can conclude this study in following three conclusions:

- Study context Insecurity is significantly higher in upper class than that of lower class.
- Study context Insecurity is significantly higher in rural area than that city area youth.
- Study context Insecurity is insignificant between girls and boys.

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To study fixed point of a function using numerical methods of finding roots of an equation and transformation matrices in 2D.

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to study fixed point of a function with help of iterative methods for finding roots, transformation matrices in two dimensional space and relation between fixed point of a function and roots of the function which rotated about the origin.

INTRODUCTION

A function $y=f(x)$ is continuous and derivable on the interval $[a,b]$ has root in $[a,b]$ (i.e. intersection point of graph of the function and X-axis), then the function $f_{(45^\circ)}(x)$ has fixed point in $[a',b']$ (i.e. intersection point of graph of the function and $y=x$ line) and vice versa, where $f_{(45^\circ)}(x)$ is function obtained by rotating $f(x)$ about the origin through the angle 45° and a',b' are projections of the points a and b on X-axis after rotating the points a,b about the origin through the angle 45° .

We discuss the problem of finding approximate solutions of the equation $f(x)=0$. In some cases it is possible to find the exact roots of the equation. e. g. when $f(x)$ is a quadratic or cubic polynomial. Otherwise, in general, one is interested in finding approximate solutions (to algebraic or transcendental or combination of both equations) using some (numerical) methods; i) Bisection Method, ii)